

Tailored Electromagnetic Properties of NiZn Nanocomposite Materials

Paul Parsons^{1,2}, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Kate Duncan³, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Shashi P. Karna¹, *Senior Member, IEEE*, John Q. Xiao⁴, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract — Nickel-zinc ferrite nanoparticles with compositions of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, where $x = 0.1 - 0.9$, were synthesized using a water-based precipitation technique. These nanoparticles were then calcined at high temperature to improve crystallinity and were characterized to determine their magnetic and dielectric properties. After selecting the synthesized composition with the most favorable magnetodielectric properties and dispersing it into a polymer matrix, we can tailor the permeability and permittivity based on the fraction of filler loading. The nanoparticles and nanocomposites were characterized using standard technologies for structural, physical, and electromagnetic properties.

Index Terms – Nanomagnetics, Nanomaterials: Synthesis and Characterization, Applications and Enabled Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetodielectric materials (MDMs) are a class of materials with nontrivial dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r(\omega)$ and magnetic permeability $\mu_r(\omega)$, where $\epsilon_r(\omega) = \epsilon(\omega)' - j\epsilon(\omega)''$ is the relative permittivity and $\mu_r(\omega) = \mu(\omega)' - j\mu(\omega)''$ is the relative permeability [2]. MDMs could possess a large value of the index of refraction $n = \sqrt{\epsilon_r(\omega)\mu_r(\omega)}$, which can significantly suppress the electromagnetic wavelength inside the medium so as to miniaturize the microwave device size such as antenna. The antenna bandwidth ($\propto 1/\epsilon_r(\omega)$) can also be dramatically improved because MDMs allow the use of substrate materials of smaller $\epsilon_r(\omega)$. Finally, it is possible to match the impedance of the substrate materials $Z/Z_{\text{Air}} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_r(\omega)}{\epsilon_r(\omega)}}$ to that of air with matched $\epsilon_r(\omega) = \mu_r(\omega)$. One of approaches to tailor the values of $\epsilon_r(\omega)$ and $\mu_r(\omega)$ is to embed magnetic inclusion of high $\mu_r(\omega)$ into low loss polymer matrix. NiZn ferrite, a soft magnetic material, has been shown to exhibit high permeability at very high to ultra high frequencies (30–300 MHz and 0.3–3 GHz, respectively). In this research, we first adjust the composition of NiZn magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) in order to maximize $\mu_r(\omega)$ in calcined NPs. We further tailor

the EM properties in polymer composition consisting NiZn inclusions.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

1. Ni-substitution in Ferrite.

MZnFe_2O_4 , where $M = \text{Ni, Mn, Co, etc.}$, is a spinel ferrite, a typical soft magnetic material with high permeability and low loss. The unit cell consists of octahedral (A) and tetrahedral (B) sites, which are occupied by metal ions (8 in A-sites, and 16 in B-sites) in addition to 32 O^{2-} ions, for a total of 56 ions [3]. The interstitial sites, A and B, are surrounded by 4 and 6 O^{2-} ions, respectively. For normal spinel structures, the divalent M^{2+} ion occupies the A site, where trivalent Fe^{3+} occupies the B site. However, in inverse spinels, half of the Fe^{3+} ions occupy the A-sites, while the remaining Fe^{3+} and Me^{2+} ions occupy the B-sites. In most cases, Zn^{2+} ions prefer the tetrahedral positions and produce normal spinels, while Ni^{2+} ions prefer the octahedral positions and produce inverse spinels [4]. Normal and inverse spinels structures can be combined, resulting in a mixed spinel structure. By controlling the amount of Ni^{2+} ions, we can preferentially tailor the spinel structure to an inverse type (Ni-rich) or normal type (Zn-rich). It has been shown that by combining mixed ferrites using a non-magnetic oxide, such as Zn ferrite (normal), with an inverse spinel will sometimes result in an increased molar magnetic moment and can be expressed as [3]:

$$M = \{(1+x)5 + (1-x)n\}\mu_B - (1-x)5\mu_B \quad (1)$$

where M is the molar magnetic moment, n is the magnetic moment contribution by M^{2+} , x is the number of moles, and μ_B is the Bohr magneton. Using the magnetic moments of ions such as Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} , we see the theoretically predicted values of the magnetic moments of increasing values of x in Fig. 1. We expect an increasing value of magnetic moment as x increases; however, it has been experimentally observed that as the solid solution becomes more Zn-rich it becomes more antiferromagnetic, resulting in a decrease of the magnetic moment at high x . This behaviour has been explained by Ishikawa as the formation of superparamagnetic spin clusters produced by the breaking of exchange paths by non-magnetic Zn ions [3, 5]. It has been shown that highest magnetic moment of the $\text{Ni}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ system resides approximately $x = 0.5$ [6].

¹ US Army Research Laboratory, Weapons and Materials Research Directorate, Aberdeen Proving Grounds, MD USA 21005

² University of Delaware, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Newark, DE USA 19716

³ US Army, Communications-Electronics Research, Development and Engineering Center, Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate, Aberdeen Proving Grounds, MD USA 21005

⁴ University of Delaware, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Newark, DE USA 19716

*Contacting Author: Paul Parsons is with the University of Delaware, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Newark, DE, USA (phone: 410-278-0990; email: pparsons@udel.edu).

Fig. 1 Magnetic moment of $M_xZn_{1-x}Fe_2O_4$, where $M = Ni^{2+}, Mn^{2+}, Co^{2+}$, the points represent the experimentally measured values.

We are interested in seeing if this phenomenon occurs at the nanoscale, and how this affects the frequency-dependent EM properties of composite materials.

2. Ferrite Synthesis

The synthesis method of the $Ni_xZn_{1-x}Fe_2O_4$ MNPs used in this study were developed using a water-based coprecipitation reaction and is described in a previously reported paper [7]. Here, we investigate the effects of adjusting the atomic content of Ni, x , from 0.1 – 0.9 as an effort to optimize the EM properties at specific frequencies. The co-precipitate yielded ferrite MNPs that are prone to aggregate into clusters, as can be seen in the JEOL-3010 transmission electron microscope (TEM) scan of two compositions (Figs. 2 & 3). The Zn-rich ferrite in Fig. 2 has spherical-shaped particles, while the Ni-rich ferrite in Fig. 3 has cubic-shaped particles. Despite the aggregation, the image indicates that the particles are on the order of 10^2 's of nanometers in size, and they possibly exhibit superparamagnetic behavior, resulting in poor magnetization at room temperature [8]. To increase the room temperature magnetization of these as-prepared nanoparticles, we increase the grain size through calcination such that they grow to some critical diameter and out of the superparamagnetic regime. Compositions were calcined in air at 800, 900, and 1000 °C for 2 h and characterized using Rigaku Ultima IV x-ray diffractometer (XRD) and a LakeShore 7404 vibrating sample magnetometer with an applied field of 1T.

Fig. 2 TEM image of as-prepared $Ni_{0.1}Zn_{0.9}Fe_2O_4$ nanoparticles with corresponding scale bar of 20 nm.

Fig. 3 TEM image of as-prepared $Ni_{0.9}Zn_{0.1}Fe_2O_4$ nanoparticles with corresponding scale bar of 20 nm.

3. Nanocomposite Fabrication

The calcined materials were ground into a fine powder and then combined with a low-loss ($\epsilon_r = 2.3$, $\tan\delta_e = 0.001$) high-density polyethylene (HDPE) powder in various loadings by percent mass (20%–80%). Losses contributed by the polymer are negligible compared to that of ferrite. The MNP/HDPE mix was heated to the melt temperature of HDPE and pressed into thin films. This process was repeated several times to promote MNP-uniformity throughout the composite material. These samples were prepared into disc and toroidal geometries by a melt-press method to be tested using the Agilent Impedance Analyzer E4991A from 0.05–1 GHz at room temperature using the dielectric and magnetic test fixtures, 16453A and 16454A, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The as-prepared states of all compositions have broad peaks seen in Fig. 4, as commonly observed for nanoparticles. As x increases, we have seen the formation of an Fe_2O_3 peak at $2\theta \approx 40^\circ$ for the as-prepared samples. Only after the powder has been calcined, has pure phase of $(Ni_xZn_{1-x})Fe_2O_4$ been observed.

Fig. 4 XRD pattern of as-prepared $Ni_xZn_{1-x}Fe_2O_4$ nanoparticles, for a) $x = 0.1$, b) $x = 0.3$, c) $x = 0.5$, and d) $x = 0.7$. For increasing amounts of Ni, a Fe_2O_3 peak is shown at approximately $2\theta = 40^\circ$.

The normalized XRD pattern for a selected composition ($Ni_{0.1}Zn_{0.9}Fe_2O_4$) that has been calcined is shown in Fig. 5.

The calcined ferrites at 800, 900, and 1000 °C have sharper peaks, indicating grain growth. The grain size can be estimated using the Scherrer equation [9]:

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}, \quad (2)$$

where D is the average crystallite size, K is the shape factor (in this case, 0.9 for spherical particles), λ is the wavelength of the x-ray, $\text{Cu}_{K\alpha 1} = 1.54\text{\AA}$, β is the FWHM, and θ is the Bragg angle.

Fig. 5 Diffraction pattern of $\text{Ni}_{0.1}\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles for the as-prepared and calcined at 800, 900, and 1000 °C samples.

These particles have grown in size between 40–80 nm, and the measured peaks of all compositions behave in a similar manner and match the corresponding JCPDS 8-324 diffraction pattern post-calcination. This grain growth improves the room temperature magnetization, M . The magnetization curves of the similarly treated $\text{Ni}_{0.9}\text{Zn}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ sample are shown in Fig. 6. We see weak magnetization for the as-prepared state ($22 \text{ Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$), but it improves as the calcine temperature increases (43 , 50 , and $56 \text{ Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$ for 800, 900, and 1000 °C, respectively).

Fig. 6 Room temperature magnetization loop of $\text{Ni}_{0.9}\text{Zn}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ samples for the as-prepared and calcined 800, 900, and 1000 °C samples.

The coercivity, H_c , initially starts at 107 mT and begins to increase as the crystallite grows in size, but after increasing past a certain size, the coercivity decreases. This behavior is attributed to the dependence on coercive force on grain size, where the exchange correlation length exceeds, equals to, or is smaller than the intergranular distance [10 - 12]. The measured coercivities are 107, 151, 150, and 95 mT for the as-prepared, 800, 900, and 1000 °C samples, respectively.

Frequency-dependent permeability and permittivity measurements were performed using an impedance analyzer from 0.05 – 1 GHz at room temperature. The relative complex permeability, μ_r , is the ratio of the permeability of the tested material,

$$\mu_r = \mu' - j\mu'', \quad (3)$$

to that of free space, μ_0 . A similar expression is used to define the complex relative permittivity, ϵ_r . The relative permeability is dependent on the inductive components of the complex impedance,

$$Z^* = R_s + j\omega L_s \quad (4)$$

where, R_s is the series resistance, L_s is the series inductance, and ω is the angular frequency [13]. The relative permeability is then calculated by assembling the following equation,

$$\mu_r = \frac{2\pi(Z_m^* - Z_{sm}^*)}{j\omega\mu_0 \ln\left(\frac{c}{b}\right)} + 1 \quad (5)$$

where, Z_m^* is the measured impedance of the toroid, Z_{sm}^* is the impedance of the air gap, h is the height of the toroid, c and b are the outer and inner diameters of the toroid, respectively.

The parallel capacitance of the material defines the relative permittivity,

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{tC_p}{A\epsilon_0} - j\frac{t}{A\omega R_p\epsilon_0} \quad (6)$$

where t is the thickness of the plate, C_p is the parallel capacitance, A is the area of the electrode, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, and R_p is the parallel resistance.

The loss tangents of both permeability and permittivity are related to the respective, complex components,

$$\tan\delta_m = \frac{\mu''}{\mu'}, \quad \tan\delta_e = \frac{\epsilon''}{\epsilon'}. \quad (7)$$

The mechanisms of loss are attributed to hysteretic, eddy current and anomalous losses and the total loss is expressed as [14]:

$$P_{loss} = P_h f + P_{ec} f^2 + P_{anom}. \quad (8)$$

Hysteretic losses are related to the amplitude of the magnetization and are linearly dependent on frequency. Eddy current losses are related to the resistivity of the material, the axis of magnetization, density and are proportional to the square of the frequency. Anomalous losses are attributed to ferrimagnetic and domain wall resonances, and do not contribute significantly to the

frequencies of interest. At lower frequencies, hysteresis losses are the dominant loss mechanism, but losses due to eddy currents increase rather quickly and eventually dominate the hysteretic contribution. To minimize these loss contributions, the coercivity needs to be small, which is native to soft magnetic materials, such as NiZnFe₂O₄. To reduce eddy current losses, the resistivity needs to be maximized. NiZn ferrites have a reportedly higher resistivity to other soft ferrites, such as MnZn ferrite (10⁹ Ω·cm vs. 10⁷ Ω·cm, respectively), so eddy current losses are largely suppressed [15].

In Figs. 7 & 8, we show the frequency-dependent measurements of the highest loaded nanocomposites (80%) with the materials calcined at 1000 °C. Relative permeability, μ_r , in addition to the respective loss tangents, $\tan\delta_m$, were compared between the different composition and loading parameters. We see that the effects of substitution caused significant changes to μ_r at different values of x .

Fig. 7 Magnetic properties of 80% loaded nanocomposites using 1000 °C materials.

Fig.8 Dielectric properties of 80% loaded nanocomposites using 1000 °C materials.

The data at specific frequencies are listed in Table I. It is clear that the MNP/HDPE nanocomposites behave in the theoretically predicted manner as seen in Fig. 1, and that the

maximum permeability in this series of experiments is achieved when $x = 0.5$. As the materials become more Zn-rich, the permeability almost drops to 1, which can be attributed to the reduction of Curie temperature below room temperature, in which we deduce that the system becomes increasingly antiferromagnetic [16].

TABLE I
FREQUENCY-DEPENDENT RELATIVE PERMEABILITY AND PERMITTIVITY OF 80% LOADED MNP/HDPE NANOCOMPOSITES AT 1000°C

Sample ID	μ_r	ϵ_r	μ_r	ϵ_r
	300 MHz	300 MHz	500 MHz	500 MHz
Ni _{0.1} Zn _{0.9} Fe ₂ O ₄	1.02	5.78	1.04	5.74
Ni _{0.3} Zn _{0.7} Fe ₂ O ₄	3.07	5.69	2.38	5.67
Ni _{0.5} Zn _{0.5} Fe ₂ O ₄	4.73	4.74	3.71	4.79
Ni _{0.7} Zn _{0.3} Fe ₂ O ₄	3.21	4.57	3.06	4.56
Ni _{0.9} Zn _{0.1} Fe ₂ O ₄	2.53	4.95	2.56	4.97

In all cases, one could use these materials as substrate for an antenna platform with a reduction in size; however, there would be an impedance mismatch in every case except for the Ni_{0.5}Zn_{0.5} at 300 MHz, while there is a somewhat close match for Ni_{0.5}Zn_{0.5} at 500 MHz, Ni_{0.7}Zn_{0.3} at 300 and 500 MHz.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

NiZn ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized using a conventional co-precipitation technique. The compositions were controlled to develop materials with a Ni-rich or Zn-rich structure. Measurements were performed on the as-prepared and calcined materials to determine crystalline, magnetic, and structural properties. Magnetization is weak for the co-precipitated particles but improves upon being calcined at high temperature. Nanocomposites were formed using the calcined materials and HDPE polymer at specified loading fractions to adjust the EM properties. Compositions of Ni_xZn_{1-x}Fe₂O₄, where $x = 0.5$ showed the highest permeability and best impedance matching for selected frequencies, with $x = 0.7$ being an alternative. With these criteria, substrate size can be reduced by a factor of ~ 4 . Additional research is required in optimizing EM characteristics of these materials, such as particle geometry to reduce demagnetization factors, or induced anisotropy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported in part by an appointment to the Student Research Participation Program at the US Army Research Laboratory administered by the Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education through an interagency agreement between the US Department of Energy and USARL. The research conducted at the US Army Research Laboratory was partly funded by the US Army Communications Electronics Research, Development, and

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